

Impact Analysis of WebQual, Price and e-WOM on Hotel Guest Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the influence of website quality (WebQual), price, and electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) on guest satisfaction in star-rated hotels in Batu City, a leading tourism destination in Indonesia. The rapid development of the hospitality industry, driven by the city's natural appeal and growing digitalization, highlights the importance of understanding customer satisfaction factors. Using a quantitative approach with 200 hotel guests as respondents, the study found that WebQual, price, and e-WOM significantly and positively affect guest satisfaction. Among these factors, WebQual had the most substantial impact, particularly through the dimensions of usability, information quality, and service interaction quality.

Furthermore, guest satisfaction mediated the relationship between these variables and the intention to stay again, emphasizing the critical role of digital service quality and peer reviews in shaping customer loyalty. The results suggest practical implications for hotel managers and policymakers to enhance digital platforms and service strategies to improve guest satisfaction and increase revisit intentions.

KEYWORDS: WebQual, Price, Electronic Word of Mouth, Guest Satisfaction, Star Hotels, Revisit Intention, Batu City

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has many tourist destinations spread across various provinces, and tourist destinations are the main driver for the growth of the hotel industry. Based on BPS data in 2023, the five provinces with the highest number of Hotel and other Accommodation businesses are East Java, Bali, West Java, Central Java, and D.I. Yogyakarta. East Java has the most businesses, with 4,053 businesses, or 13.63 percent of all hotel and accommodation businesses in Indonesia. Then, Bali with 3,528 businesses (11.86 percent), West Java with 3,353 businesses (11.86 percent), Central Java with 2,124 businesses (11.86 percent), and D.I. Yogyakarta with 1,709 businesses (5.75 percent).

This number of visits is inseparable from the status of Batu City, which is known as one of the leading tourist cities in Indonesia because of its potential for extraordinary natural beauty. The admiration of the Dutch nation for the beauty and natural beauty of Batu made the Batu city area aligned with a country in Europe, namely Switzerland and dubbed as De Kleine Zwitserland or Little Switzerland on the island of Java (Leyninna & Faundra, 2017).

Batu City used to be a hilly area that was often used as a tourist destination for Dutch visitors during the colonial era. The cool-air tourist city filled with apple plantations and orchid nurseries has been increasingly frequented by tourists

in recent years. This is due to the emergence of various interesting places, such as Museum Angkut, Eco Green Park, Jawa Timur Park, and Batu Night Spectacular. Batu is also increasingly recognized for its beauty because it is used as the location of paragliding competitions at national and international levels. This fact encourages hoteliers in Batu City to exist increasingly because they are faced with competition from the increasingly mushrooming hospitality industry in Batu City.

For decades, information technology has played an important role in transforming and developing the hospitality and tourism industry (Wang et al., 2021). Explicitly, as a powerful marketing and operational tool, the Internet has revolutionized business operations by providing tremendous opportunities for service providers and consumers in this industry (Amaro & Duarte, 2015). Hotels have traditionally relied on intermediaries (e.g., travel agents) to disseminate information and sell their products. However, the advent of e-commerce websites has developed new and potentially powerful communication and distribution channels for hotels, thus narrowing the gap between hotels and consumers (Ponte et al., 2015). While there is widespread recognition of the compatibility between the Internet and the hospitality industry, hotels need to understand the importance of website quality in shaping their customers' behavior (Hsu et al.,

2012). This is realized by star hotels in Batu City that have successfully launched their websites, but non-star hotels still rely entirely on intermediaries. The assessment of star hotels itself is based on a number of aspects, such as the number of rooms of at least 15 rooms with a minimum area of 20 m², available facilities ranging from basic facilities such as air conditioning, TV, and telephone to supporting facilities such as restaurants and bars.

1. Describe WebQual quality, price, e-WOM, hotel guest satisfaction, and intention to stay again at star hotels in Batu City.

2. Analyzing the impact of WebQual, price, and e-WOM on guest satisfaction of star hotels in Batu City.

1. Theoretical Benefits

The research results enrich the discussion of consumer behavior on hotel guest satisfaction determined by WebQual, price, and e-wom factors in repurchase intention.

2. Practical Benefits

For hoteliers, it can be used as an important source of information for policy making related to WebQual, price, and e-wom, which can attract consumers to come to stay again because of their perceived satisfaction.

3. Policy Benefits

It is an important source of information in policy-making for the government as a public body related to the utilization and management of websites to realize the quality and reliability of public services.

II. LITERATUR EREVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

This research examines the intention of hotel guests to stay again, where hotel guests make reservations or bookings directly on the Hotel's website without the need to come to the intended Hotel. Reservations can be made several days in advance, even several weeks or months before check-in time. On the hotel website, hotel guests can find information that is needed and desired. When visiting the Hotel's website, hotel guests can browse every feature and observe the prices offered and the service facilities that will be provided. The need for information on the website and the price offered can affect consumer satisfaction, which in turn will determine the intention to stay again in the future. When consumers are satisfied, they will give positive reviews about the Hotel; in other words, reviews or recommendations will exist if they are satisfied. However, this study looks at the opposite of how satisfaction will occur if consumers read reviews from other guests who have stayed, so a new conceptual framework is built that connects variables such as WebQual, price, e-WOM, and Hotel guest satisfaction and return stay intentions.

Kotler (2002) suggests aspects that affect consumer satisfaction in receiving service quality. These aspects include improving service quality, namely all activities included in identifying, researching, and developing new services quickly, as well as improving service quality with good service quality and appropriate prices. The second

aspect is the inventory management process (facilities provided), namely activities in the form of development and processing to improve the facilities provided to consumers. The third aspect is the booking process up to payment (administration), namely all activities in the form of ordering, approving, and paying. In this case, booking tickets is up to payment or departure. The fourth aspect is the process of service to consumers, namely all activities in the form of making it easier for consumers to get service according to their wishes, answering and solving problems from consumers.

Kotler and Keller (2007) define customer satisfaction as the level of a person's feelings as a result of the comparison between reality and expectations received by a product and service. Akbar and Parves (2009) state that satisfaction is a customer's assessment of a product or service, whether the product or service has met his needs and expectations. Customer satisfaction plays an important role because there is a big difference in loyalty between satisfied and completely satisfied customers (Lovelock & Wright, 2007).

According to (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017), the methods used to measure customer satisfaction are: 1) Complaints and Suggestion Systems, customer-focused companies make it easy for their customers to provide their suggestions and complaints. 2) Ghost shopping, namely hiring several ghost shoppers who act or pretend to be potential customers of the company's products and then assessing how the company serves specific consumer requests, answers consumer questions, and handles any complaints. 3) Lost Customer Analysis: Wherever possible, the company should be consumers who have switched to other companies in order to understand why this happened and in order to adopt the next good or improvement policy.

Given that the impact of dissatisfied customers or negative customer experiences will have a major effect on the company, it is necessary to restore customer goodwill. The procedure for restoring customer goodwill, according to Kotler and Keller (2009: 143), is to open a free 24-hour non-stop "hotline" to receive and follow up on complaints from customers, immediately contact customers who have complained, accept responsibility and customer disappointment; avoid customers being blamed. Employ someone who has high empathy in the service and responds quickly to complaints so that customers are satisfied.

WebQual is a method of measuring website quality based on the perception of end users (the public). This method is a development of servqual (Zeithaml et al., 1990), which was widely used previously to measure service quality (Diana, 2012). Website quality is the ability of a website to meet the expectations of its users and owners, as determined by a series of attributes (Morales-Vargas et al., 2020)

The quality of a website plays a crucial role in attracting users, maintaining user attendance, and increasing user satisfaction with the services provided. Therefore, analyzing user satisfaction with website quality is a very important

aspect to study and improve. Fan et al. (2013) see convenience, content, aesthetics, interactivity, and customization as indicators of Website Quality. Aggarwal and Aaskash (2018) use 7 WebQual measurements, namely SQ (System Quality), TR (Trust), CS (Customer Support), CQ (Content Quality), US (Usage), CF (Customer Feedback), and PR (Personalization).

WebQual has undergone several iterations (Barnes & Vidgen, 2002) namely WebQual 1.0 is the first version of WebQual developed in the UK Business School domain by following the standards of QFD (Barnes & Vidgen, 2002). The results of WebQual 1.0 development resulted in five dimensions, namely ease of use, experience, information, communication, and integration. WebQual 1.0 has the disadvantage that it focuses too much on the information quality aspect. After that, WebQual 2.0 was improved by adding aspects of interaction quality adapted from ServQual. Because WebQual 2.0 is too focused on making improvements from WebQual 1.0, the shortcomings of WebQual 2.0 are in the interaction quality aspect, so it pays less attention to other aspects, namely information quality. Then came WebQual 3.0, which found that website quality can be grouped into three areas, namely site quality, information quality, and service interaction quality. From the analysis on WebQual 3.0, it can be identified into three dimensions, namely usability, information quality, and service interaction quality. From WebQual 3.0, the usability dimension replaces the site quality dimension because usability emphasizes the user's point of view. In the development of WebQual, Barnes and Vidgen (2002) put forward WebQual 4.0, consisting of three dimensions: Usability, Information Quality, and Interaction Quality. Usability is the quality associated with the design of the site, for example, the appearance, then use, navigation, and the image conveyed to the user. Information Quality is the quality of the content contained on the site, whether or not the information is appropriate for user purposes such as accuracy, format, and relevance. Interaction Quality is the quality of service interactions experienced by users as they delve deeper into the site, manifested by trust and empathy, for example, issues of transaction and information security, product delivery, personalization, and communication with the site owner.

Word of Mouth (WOM) is not only limited to individuals but can be used on any platform, including the Internet, known as Electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM). Although it has similarities with traditional WOM, e-WOM provides various ways to exchange information, both valid and anonymous or even confidentially. e-WOM provides geographical freedom for people around the world to disseminate temporary information and store it permanently in written form.

Information exchange in e-WOM can be done through social media such as email, blogs, chatrooms, Facebook, Twitter, and other social media platforms that provide

interaction between consumers so that there is an exchange of information about the goods or services they get when making a purchase. Hennig-Thurau and Gwinner et al. (2004) electronic word of mouth is a form of communication marketing that contains positive or negative statements made by potential customers, customers, and former customers about a product or company, which are available to many people or institutionalized through internet media. Litvin et al. (2008) define electronic word of mouth as all informal communication aimed at consumers through internet-based technology related to the use or characteristics of certain goods and services or their sellers. So, the dimensions are characteristic of the goods, characteristic of the services, and characteristic of the sellers. Thus, e-WOM is also defined as informal communication that flows through the Internet media, both between producers and consumers and between consumers themselves. This communication is in the form of positive or negative statements about a particular product. Chua and Banerjee (2016) stated that e-WOM can be measured through reliability, specificity, and understanding.

The satisfaction of a consumer is also influenced by price. When the price is in accordance with the benefits provided, consumers will feel satisfied. Josua et al. (2017) found that price has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Similar results were also obtained by other researchers, such as Mirsya et al. (2017), Kencana (2018), and Wantara et al. (2019). Another study on customer satisfaction by Kuo and Nakhata (2019) found that positive e-WOM increases customer satisfaction, while negative e-WOM decreases customer satisfaction. When consumers are satisfied with website quality (WebQual), price, and e-WOM, it will foster the intention of consumers to make repeat purchases (repurchase intention), as found by Chang and Chou (2012), where customer satisfaction affects repurchase intention. Similar results were also obtained by Ciu et al. (2019), who found that satisfaction significantly affects repurchase intention.

III. RESEARCH METHOD AND HYPOTHESES

A. Research Design

In general, experts agree that research design is a systematic and structured plan that guides the course of research and includes important stages in the research. The research design must be prepared carefully and in detail so that it can help researchers obtain valid and useful data. Creswell (2016) suggests that a research design is a plan that includes all stages of research, such as the selection of research topics, data collection, data analysis, and interpretation of research results.

B. Population and Sample

1. Population

The population used in this study are guests who have stayed at star hotels in Batu City with an unknown number.

2. Sample

The sample used in this study were guests who stayed at the Batu City Star Hotel at least once in the last 6 months when the research was conducted with an uncertain sample size. Based on studies conducted on various estimation methods, the sample size required to reduce bias in all types of SEM estimation is 200 (Loehlin, 2004), so the number of samples used in the study was 200 hotel guests.

3. Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis used in this writing technique is:

Descriptive analysis is used by researchers to provide information about the characteristics of research variables, including data on WebQual variables, price, e-WOM, satisfaction, and return stay intention using median ranking measures and regression analysis..

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data collection through distributing questionnaires to tourists who have visited one of the tourist destinations in the district, it can be seen that the characteristics of respondents based on gender show that respondents who are guests who have stayed at Batu City hotels are 56.50% dominated by women, with the highest level of education being D3 / S1 at 47.50% at the age of 33-40 at 32%.

The frequency distribution of respondents' answers about WebQual variables based on respondents' perceptions of the Usability indicator with the distribution of respondents' answers responding to users finds it easy to learn the operation of the website obtained the most answers agreeing as many as 73 respondents (36.5%), followed by answers strongly agreeing as many as 56 respondents (28%), neutral as many as 42 respondents (21%), disagreeing as many as 21 respondents (10.5%), strongly disagreeing as many as eight respondents (4%). Average users tend to agree (3.74) find it easy to learn the operation of the website. The average user tends to agree (3.74) that it is easy to learn the operation of the website.

Respondents' perceptions of the Usability indicator, the distribution of respondents' answers to the clear website obtained answers strongly agree as many as 70 respondents (35%), followed by answers agreeing as many as 60 respondents (30%), neutral as many as 39 respondents (19.5%), disagreeing as many as 24 respondents (12%), strongly disagreeing as many as seven respondents (3.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.81) that the website is clear.

Respondents responding to users find it easy to navigate the website obtained the most answers, agreeing as many as 67 respondents (33.5%), followed by answers strongly agreeing as many as 62 respondents (31%), as many as 40 respondents (20%), disagreeing as many as 21 respondents (10.5%), strongly disagreeing as many as 10 respondents (5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.75) that users find it easy to navigate the website.

The distribution of respondents' answers responding users felt that the website was easy to operate obtained the most answers strongly agreeing as many as 74 respondents (37%), followed by answers agreeing 60 respondents (30%), neutral as many as 36 respondents (18%), disagreeing as many as 20 respondents (10%), strongly disagreeing as many as 10 respondents (5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.84) for websites that are easy to operate.

Respondents' perceptions of the website having an attractive appearance obtained the most answers strongly agreeing, as many as 68 respondents (34%), followed by answers agreeing 63 respondents (31.5%), neutral as many as 43 respondents (21.5%), disagreeing as many as 17 respondents (8.5%), strongly disagreeing as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.82) that the website should have an attractive appearance.

The distribution of respondents' answers to unique website design obtained answers agree as many as 69 respondents (34.5%), followed by answers strongly agree 65 respondents (32.5%), neutral as many as 40 respondents (20%), disagree as many as 17 respondents (8.5%), strongly disagree as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.82) with unique website design.

Respondents responded that the website has good performance; most answers agreed as many as 75 respondents (37.5%), followed by answers strongly agree 52 respondents (26%), neutral as many as 43 respondents (21.5%), disagree as many as 21 respondents (10.5%), strongly disagree as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.70) that the website has good performance.

The average perception of respondents on the usability indicator obtained a score of 3.78, which means that respondents tend to agree that usability contributes to WebQual. Website items are easy to operate and are most appreciated when describing usability.

On the information quality indicator, it was found that the website provides clear information; the most answers were agreed by 68 respondents (34%), followed by answers strongly agreed by 63 respondents (31.5%), neutral by 41 respondents (20.5%), disagreed by 19 respondents (9.5%), strongly disagreed by nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.78) that the website provides clear information.

In the distribution of respondents' answers to trusted website information obtained, most answers agree, as many as 64 respondents (32%), followed by answers strongly agree 60 respondents (30%), as many as 52 respondents (26%), disagree as many as 15 respondents (7.5%), strongly disagree as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.79) that website information can be trusted.

Respondents responded that the availability of up-to-date information from the website obtained the most answers, strongly agreeing as many as 68 respondents (34%),

followed by answers agreeing 60 respondents (30%), neutral as many as 41 respondents (20.5%), disagreeing as many as 21 respondents (10.5%), strongly disagreeing as many as 10 respondents (5.0%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.78) with the website providing up-to-date information.

The distribution of respondents' answers to the website providing the information needed obtained the most answers strongly agreeing, as many as 76 respondents (38%), followed by answers agreeing 60 respondents (30%), as many as 33 respondents (16.5%), disagreeing as many as 22 respondents (11%), strongly disagreeing as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.86) that the website should provide the information needed.

Respondents responding to the website providing information that is easy to understand obtained the most answers strongly agreeing as many as 69 respondents (34.5%), followed by answers agreeing 62 respondents (31.0%), neutral as many as 42 respondents (21.0%), disagreeing as many as 18 respondents (9.0%), strongly disagreeing as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.82) that the website provides information that is easy to understand.

Respondents' perceptions of the website providing complete information obtained the most answers strongly agreeing as many as 70 respondents (35.0%), followed by answers agreeing 64 respondents (32%), neutral as many as 36 respondents (18.0%), disagreeing as many as 20 respondents (10%), strongly disagreeing as many as 10 respondents (5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.82) with websites providing complete information.

The distribution of respondents' answers to the website providing information in the right format obtained the most agreed answers, as many as 64 respondents (32%), followed by answers strongly agree 63 respondents (31.5%), neutral as many as 40 respondents (20%), disagree as many as 24 respondents (12%), strongly disagree as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.74) with websites providing information in the right format.

The average score on the information quality indicator is 3.79, which means that respondents tend to agree that information quality contributes to WebQual. The item providing the information I need is most appreciated when describing information quality.

The distribution of respondents' answers to the quality indicators of service interaction for the website representing the Hotel's reputation obtained the most answers agreeing as many as 74 respondents (37%), followed by answers strongly agreeing 55 respondents (27.5%), neutral as many as 42 respondents (21%), disagreeing as many as 20 respondents (10%), strongly disagreeing as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.73) that the website represents the Hotel's reputation.

Respondents responded to safe transactions on the hotel website; most answers agreed, as many as 70 respondents (35%), followed by neutral answers from 53 respondents (26.5%), strongly agreed, as many as 47 respondents (23.5%), disagreed as many as 21 respondents (10.5%), strongly disagreed as many as nine respondents (4.5%). The average respondent tends to agree (3.63) to safely transact on the hotel website. Hypothesis one is that WebQual, price, and e-WOM have a positive and significant effect on guest satisfaction of star hotels in Batu City. The results of the analysis of hypothesis one testing can be seen in Table 19.

The Effect of Website Quality, Price, and E-Wom on Guest Satisfaction

Variabels	Estimate	p-value	Result
Website Quality	0,514	0,000	Positive, Significant
E-Wom	0,218	0,000	Positive, Significant

Source : Primary data processed, 2025

The Effect of WebQual on hotel guest satisfaction results in a Cr value of 8.976 with a p-value of 0.000. The p-value is smaller than the statistical significance at $\alpha = 5\%$, so it can be said that WebQual has a positive and significant effect on hotel guest satisfaction. These results indicate that the more web quality there is, the more customer satisfaction increases.

The Effect of price on hotel guest satisfaction results in a Cr value of 4.797 with a p-value of 0.000. The p-value is smaller than the statistical significance at $\alpha = 5\%$, so it can be said that price has a positive and significant effect on hotel guest satisfaction. These results indicate that the more affordable the price offered, the more customer satisfaction increases.

In this study, WebQual is described through the quality of information in which there is information needed. One of the information needed by guests is information about prices. Guests will assess whether the price is equivalent to the type of room offered while reading reviews about prices from previous guests who have stayed at the Hotel; if the hotel website provides convenience in payment, guests will feel satisfied, which will make guests intend to stay again in the future even though there are relatively the same prices offered by other hotels.

The results of this study prove that webQual, price, and e-WOM affect the intention to stay again through guest satisfaction with star hotels in Batu City, meaning that when guests get the information needed on the website, and the price offered is more attractive than class hotels, and there are recommendations from other guests who have stayed, it will increase guest satisfaction, which in turn will increase their intention to stay again at the Hotel. This finding is in line with previous research conducted by Shin Ji et al. (2013), which provides results that WebQual affects

repurchase intention through customer satisfaction, and research by Zimbali et al. (2024) provides results that price affects repurchase intention through customer satisfaction and research by Surya & Setiawan (2024), Sya'roni & Fikriah (2024) provides results that e-WOM affects repurchase intention through customer satisfaction. Tandon et al. (2020) also provide results that show that e-WOM and WebQual affect repurchase intention through customer satisfaction.

An additional finding in this study is that WebQual most influences repurchase intention through satisfaction. The characteristics of respondents who are mostly female and the majority of D3 / S1 educated in this study generally show that women pay more attention to design details, attractive photos, and more complete information about facilities or services and other information needed, which creates satisfaction, which further increases the preference for repurchase intention. Individuals with higher levels of education are generally more sensitive to the quality of appearance, navigation, and information presented on the website, which can increase satisfaction and, in turn, encourage the intention to stay again.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion described in the previous chapters, it can be concluded as follows:

1. WebQual is formed by usability, information quality, and service interaction quality. The biggest contribution to forming WebQuest is information quality, which provides the information needed. E-WOM is formed by intensity, opinion value, and content. The largest contribution to forming e-WOM is the value of opinion, namely recommendations from guests who have stayed at star hotels. Guest satisfaction is formed by matching expectations, ease of obtaining, and satisfaction with the overall service. The largest contribution to forming guest satisfaction is the suitability of expectations, namely the price offered according to expectations because the price is comparable to the services provided. Re-stay intentions are formed by transactional intentions, referential intentions, preferential intentions, and exploratory intentions. The largest contribution to forming the intention to stay again is the referential intention, namely giving a description to others about the quality of the Hotel.

2. WebQual, price, and e-WOM affect guest satisfaction with star hotels in Batu City. The availability of the required information about the price on the website and the price is equivalent to the type of room offered, and reviews from other guests who have stayed at the Hotel about the price offered will make guests feel satisfied as the website provides convenience in payment.

Based on the research results and conclusions that have been stated, the suggestions put forward in this study are as follows:

3. Practically speaking

a. For business people, especially in the hotel industry, it is recommended to increase e-WOM through the website by providing a QR code at the reception desk as a means for hotel guests to provide reviews based on their experience staying at the Hotel.

b. For associations such as the Indonesian Hotel and Restaurant Association (PHRI), it is recommended that they make appropriate policies on limiting the highest and lowest prices based on hotel class to improve the quality and competitiveness of the hospitality industry in Indonesia.

c. For the Batu City Government to prepare Juanda airport shuttle services through a fleet owned by the Batu City government to increase the attractiveness of visits to Batu City so as to make a positive contribution to regional economic growth through increased income, employment, and other economic activities around the Hotel.

d. For future researchers to develop this research model on different types of businesses that use websites.

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